

MOSLANGAN MANBALI AB TIZIMI HAQIDA

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AB tizimi

$$A_{xt} - \alpha A - \beta AB = 0, \quad B_x + \frac{\gamma}{2}(|A|^2)_t = 0,$$

Ikki qatlamli dissipativ tizimni tavsiflovchi muhim modellardan biri bo'lib, bunda har bir qatlamdagi tezliklar o'zgarmas, ammo tezlik siljishi nolga teng emas. Bu yerda A va B mos ravishda kompleks va haqiqiy to'lqin amplitudalari bo'lib, ikki xil qatlamdagi to'lqinlar harakatini ifodalaydi. α , β va γ - haqiqiy o'zgarmaslardir.

AB tizimining muhim xossalardan biri shundaki, u ikkita chiziqli tizimning moslik sharti, ya'ni Laks juftligi orqali ifodalanadi. Bu esa tadqiqotlarga uni teskari sochilish transformatsiyasi usuli yordamida o'rganish imkonini beradi [1]. (1) tenglamalar sistemasiga mos Laks juftligi quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$f_x = \begin{pmatrix} -i\lambda & \frac{\sqrt{\beta\gamma}}{2}A^* \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\beta\gamma}}{2}A & i\lambda \end{pmatrix} f, \quad f_t = \frac{1}{4i\lambda} \begin{pmatrix} -\alpha - \beta B & \frac{\sqrt{\beta\gamma}}{2}A_t^* \\ \frac{\sqrt{\beta\gamma}}{2}A_t & \alpha + \beta B \end{pmatrix} f,$$

bu yerda yulduzcha $*$ kompleks qo'shmani bildiradi. (1) tenglamalar sistemasi $\beta\gamma$ ko'paytmaning ishorasiga bog'liq holda turli xil yechimlarga ega. So'nggi yillarda Z. Yan va boshqalar [2,3] bu tenglamalar sistemasining modulyatsion beqarorligini o'rgandilar hamda umumlashtirilgan Darbu transformatsiyalari yordamida $\beta\gamma > 0$ va $\beta\gamma < 0$ holatlarida yechimlarning uzoq vaqtli asimptotikasini tadqiq etdilar.

Yuqorida zikr etilgan ishlarda tizim (1) uchun $x \rightarrow \infty$ da A funksiyasi nolga, B esa birlikka yetarlicha tez yaqinlashuvchi chegaraviy shartlar qaralgan. Ta'kidlash joizki, ushbu chegaraviy shartlarda $\beta\gamma < 0$ bo'lganda soliton yechimlar mavjud emas. Biroq Y. Zhai, L. Wei, X. Geng, L. Tao [4, 5] Riman-Gilbert usuli yordamida $|A| \rightarrow 1$, $B \rightarrow 0$ ($x \rightarrow \infty$ da) chegaraviy shartlar ostida AB tizimi breather turidagi yechimlarga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdilar. Xususan, $\alpha = 0$, $\beta = 1$ va $\gamma = -1$ bo'lganda, tizim (1) quyidagi standart AB tizimiga keladi:

$$A_{xt} - AB = 0, \quad B_x - \frac{1}{2}(|A|^2)_t = 0. \quad (2)$$

(2) tenglamalar sistemasi ham sochilish nazariyasining teskari masalasi usuli yordamida yechilishi mumkin. Sochilish nazariyasining teskari usuli moslangan manbali soliton tenglamalarni tahlil qilish va ularning soliton yechimlarini topishda qulay usul hisoblanadi. Ushbu usul fokuslovchi va defokuslovchi nochiziqli Shredinger tenglamalari, sine-Gordon tenglamasi, modifikatsiyalangan Kortevge-de Friz tenglamasi, Hirota tenglamasi [7] va boshqa ko'plab soliton tenglamalarni o'rganishda keng qo'llanilgan. Mazkur ish cheksizlikda nol bo'lmagan chegaraviy shartlar ostida, moslangan manbaga ega AB tizimini Sochilish nazariyasining teskari usuli yordamida integrallashga bag'ishlangan.

Quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini qaraymiz:

$$A_{xt} - AB = 2i \sum_{n=1}^N (f_{1,n}^{*2} + f_{2,n}^2), \quad B_x - \frac{1}{2}(|A|^2)_t = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial f_{1,n}}{\partial x} = -i\lambda_n f_{1,n} + \frac{1}{2}A^* f_{2,n}, \quad \frac{\partial f_{2,n}}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2}A f_{1,n} + i\lambda_n f_{2,n}, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Boshlang'ich shart:

$$A(x, 0) = A_0(x), \quad x \in R.$$

Bu yerda $A_0(x)$ funksiya silliq bo'lib, quyidagi shartni qanoatlantiradi.

$$(1 + |x|)(A_0(x) - 2\rho e^{i\theta_{\pm}}) \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{\pm}),$$

bu yerda θ_{\pm} soni $(0, \pi)$ oraliqdagi o'zgarmas sonlar, ρ esa musbat haqiqiy o'zgarmas deb olinadi. Quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasi

$$\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x} = -i\lambda f_1 + \frac{1}{2}A_0^*(x)f_2,$$

$$\frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2}A_0(x)f_1 + i\lambda f_2$$

aniq N ta diskret xos qiymatlarga, ya'ni $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_N$ ga ega deb faraz qilamiz.

Mazkur tadqiqotda sochilish nazariyasini teskari masalasi usuli yordamida AB tizimining (1)-(2) boshlang'ich masalasi quyidagi shartlar ostida o'rganiladi:

1) $f_n(x, t) = (f_{1,n}, f_{2,n})^T$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ funksiyalar tizim (2) ning λ_n ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$) xos qiymatlariga mos xos funksiyalari bo'lib, ular quyidagi normallashtirish shartini qanoatlantiradi:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_n^T(x, t) f_n^*(x, t) dx = a_n^2(t), \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N,$$

bu yerda $a_n(t)$ lar t ning nolga teng bo'lmagan uzluksiz skalyar funksiyalaridir;

2) $A(x, t)$ va $B(x, t)$ yechimlari yetarlicha differensiallanuvchi bo'lib, ularning barcha hosilalari bilan birga $|x| \rightarrow \infty$ da $|x|^{-1}$ ning istalgan darajasidan tezroq o'z limitlariga intiladi. Barcha $t \geq 0$ lar uchun ular quyidagi asimptotik chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiradi [6]:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} A(x, t) = 2\rho e^{i\theta_{\pm} + \frac{i}{2\rho}t}, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} B(x, t) = 0,$$

hamda quyidagi normallashtirish sharti bajariladi:

$$|A_t|^2 - B^2 = 1.$$

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Zhai Y., Wei L., Geng X., Wei J., *Multi-bright-dark soliton solutions to the AB system in nonlinear optics*, Communications in Theoretical Physics, 74 (2022), No. 4, 045003.
2. Chen S., Yan Z., *Long-time asymptotics of solutions for the coupled dispersive AB system with initial value problems*, Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications, 498 (2021), No. 2, 124966.
3. Wen X.-Y., Yan Z., *Modulational instability and higher-order rogue waves with parameters modulation in a coupled integrable AB system via the generalized Darboux transformation*, Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science, 25 (2015), No. 12, 123115.
4. Zhai Y., Wei L., Geng X., Tao L., *Breather solutions to the AB system with non-zero background*, Journal of Geometry and Physics, 190 (2023), 104858.
5. Zhai Y., Tao L., Wei J., Geng X., *On the two nonzero boundary problems of the AB system with*

multiple poles, Chaos, Solitons & Fractals, 188 (2024), 115560.

6. Khasanov A. B., Reyimberganov A. A., “On the AB system with a self-consistent source”, *Алгебра и анализ*, **37**:4 (2025), 149–165

7. Khasanov A. B., Reyimberganov A. A., “On the Hirota equation with a self-consistent source”, *Theoret. and Math. Phys.*, **221**:2 (2024), 1852–1866

